

As the condensation products⁴ of hydrazides with aldehydes and ketones have shown considerable antitubercular activity, we have synthesised a large number of *N*¹-(*N*-aryl-glycyl)-*N*²-(arylidene or alkylidene)hydrazines of *N*-4-diphenylglycyl and *N*-2-naphthyl-glycyl hydrazides. The hydrazides were synthesised by the hydrazinolysis of the corresponding ethyl esters, prepared in the usual manner.

Several semicarbazides and thiosemicarbazides have also been synthesised by condensing hydrazides with α -naphthylisocyanate and phenyl isothiocyanate⁵ (or with *NN*-diarylthioureas)⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Thiazolylglycines.—A mixture of the heterocyclic amine (1.5 *M*), monochloroacetic acid (1*M*), and sodium acetate (2 *M*), dissolved in a minimum amount of water, was heated at 50-60° on a water bath for 1 to 2 hours. The solid obtained on cooling was washed with water, treated with 10% aqueous ammonium carbonate solution, and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with HCl. The neutralised solution was left overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitate, thus formed, was washed with ether to remove the imino derivative [thiazolyl *N* (CH₂COOH)₂], which was formed as a byproduct, and the residue was crystallised from benzene.

N-2-Thiazolylglycine was prepared by the above method; m.p.* 218-25°, yield 50%. (Found: N, 17.43. C₈H₆O₂N₂S requires N, 17.72%.)

4-Methyl-*N*-2-thiazolylglycine was prepared by the above method; m.p. 200-205°, yield 20%. (Found: N, 15.86. C₈H₈O₂N₂S requires N, 16.25%.)

Ethyl Esters of N-Arylglycines.—Primary arylamine (1 *M*), ethyl chloroacetate (1*M*), and sodium acetate (2 *M*), dissolved in minimum water, were heated together on a steam bath for 1 hour. After cooling, water was added and the precipitate formed was recrystallised from light petroleum.

N-Arylglycyl Hydrazides.—A solution of the ethyl ester of the corresponding *N*-arylglycines and 2 moles of 95% hydrazine hydrate in ethanol were refluxed for 4 to 5 hours on a steam bath. The solvent was removed and the product recrystallised from ethanol.

o-Cresotic acid hydrazide was prepared from the ethyl ester of *o*-cresotic acid and 95% hydrazine hydrate.

*N*¹-(*N*-Arylglycyl)-*N*²-(arylidene or alkylidene)hydrazines.—To a boiling ethanolic solution of the freshly distilled appropriate aromatic aldehyde or ketone the corresponding hydrazide was added in equimolar amounts. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hour. When a ketone was taken, the refluxing was continued for 4 to 5 hours. The solid product separating on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from acetone. The properties are recorded in Tables I and II.

4. Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1358; Misra and Khare, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 323.

5. Buu-Hoi *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2160.

6. Runti and Collino, *Boll. Chim. Form.*, 1961, **100**, 837.

TABLE I

*N*¹-(*N*-4-Diphenylglycyl)-*N*²-(arylidene or alkylidene)hydrazines.

No.	Aldehyde or ketone.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	Salicylaldehyde	217-20°	90%	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	12.82	12.16
2	Anisaldehyde	126°	95	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	11.18	11.60
3	<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzaldehyde	122-23°	95	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	12.48	12.16
4	Vanillin	120-21°	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	10.86	11.20
5	2-Bromo-5-methoxybenzaldehyde	178°	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Br	9.36	9.58
6	<i>p</i> -Chloroacetophenone	165-74°	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ON ₃ Cl	11.46	11.09
7	β -Naphthaldehyde	231°*	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ ON ₃	11.02	11.06
8	Acetone	178-80°	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ ON ₃	15.14	14.94
9	<i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	162°	85	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ ON ₃	12.66	12.20
10	Diethyl ketone	138-40°	60	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ ON ₃	14.10	13.59
11	<i>p</i> -Isopropylbenzaldehyde	190-95°*	60	C ₂₄ H ₂₅ ON ₃	11.63	11.32
12	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	190-96°*	99	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₄	16.98	16.38
13	Benzaldehyde	185°	85	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ ON ₃	12.38	12.76
14	Cinnamaldehyde	165-71°	45	C ₂₅ H ₂₉ ON ₃	11.55	11.79
15	Piperonaldehyde	170-74°	90	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃	10.82	11.22
16	Furfuraldehyde	200°	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	13.56	13.16
17	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	170°	88	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ON ₃ Cl	11.10	11.55

TABLE II

*N*¹-(*N*-2-Naphthylglycyl)-*N*²-(arylidene)hydrazines.

No.	Aldehyde.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	Salicylaldehyde	175-80°	95%	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	13.36	13.16
2	Anisaldehyde	147°	88	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	12.25	12.70
3	Piperonaldehyde	123-25°	60	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	12.43	12.10
4	Furfuraldehyde	185-87°	56	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	14.92	14.33
5	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	200-202°	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ ON ₃ Cl	12.32	12.82
6	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	200-205°*	95	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄	14.47	14.07

1-Acyl-4-aryl Semicarbazides.— A mixture of the corresponding hydrazide (0.05*M*) in benzene and α -naphthyl isocyanate (0.05*M*) was refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1 hour at 60-70°. The contents were cooled and the product obtained was crystallised from a suitable solvent.

TABLE III

1-Acyl-4-(α -naphthyl) semicarbazides.

No.	Acyl group.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>N</i> -4-Diphenylglycyl	222-25°	85%	C ₂₅ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₄	13.32	13.63
2	<i>N</i> -2-Naphthylglycyl	230-40°	50	C ₂₃ H ₂₉ O ₂ N ₄	14.16	14.56
3	<i>o</i> -Cresotic	214-15°	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	12.82	12.53

1-Acyl-4-aryl Thiosemicarbazides

Method I.—An equimolar mixture of the hydrazide and phenyl isothiocyanate in benzene was refluxed for half an hour. The product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Method II.—To a boiling ethanolic solution of *NN'*-diarylthiourea (0.01*M*) an ethanolic solution of the appropriate hydrazide (0.01 *M*) was added. The contents were refluxed on a water bath for 1½ to 2 hours. On concentration and cooling, a solid separated which was recrystallised from ethanol. The properties are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV
1-Acyl-4-arylthiosemicarbazide.

No.	R.	R'.	RNH-C-NHNHCOR'			%Nitrogen	
			M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1	Ph		170°	68%	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ ON ₂ S	14.52	14.89
2	Ph		186-90°	85	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	15.52	16.00
3	Ph		180°	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S	13.45	13.85
4	Ph.CH ₃	Do	153-56°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S	13.15	13.33
5	Ph.CH ₃		180°	99	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ ON ₂ S	15.05	14.35

N.B. Melting points marked with an asterisk denote decomposition on heating.

1-(*N*-2-naphthylglycyl)-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide was prepared only by method I.

1-(*N*-4-Diphenylglycyl)-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide and 1-(*o*-cresotic)-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide were also prepared by method I.

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